

Towards *in situ* de-risking of lunar granular materials handling: Design, manufacture and initial testing of a remotely reconfigurable multi-sample wedge hopper breadboard suitable for parabolic flight with lunar gravity and vacuum conditions

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Abstract

The effective handling of granular materials (regolith) in the lunar environment - characterised by reduced gravity (1/6g) and a hard vacuum exosphere - remains a critical yet poorly understood challenge for future In-Situ Resource Utilisation (ISRU). Current Earth-based knowledge lacks validation against real lunar conditions, creating a risk of hardware and process failure for future lunar surface applications. This study details the design, manufacture, and initial testing of a remotely reconfigurable wedge hopper breadboard developed to bridge this gap. The system is specifically designed to operate within a vacuum chamber during lunar-gravity parabolic flights, enabling the generation of appropriate fidelity validation datasets.

The breadboard features a remotely adjustable geometry (hopper wall angle and outlet width) and a carousel dosing device capable of sequentially dispensing multiple granular samples into the hopper without breaking vacuum. Functional testing in a laboratory vacuum chamber successfully demonstrated the system's ability to perform multiple filling, static storage, and controlled discharge cycles, as well as an autonomous recovery protocol for clearing blockages - a prerequisite for remote flight operations. Mechanical function of the breadboard was verified and vacuum characterisation revealed outgassing from the commercial-off-the-shelf components requiring an appropriate thermal vacuum conditioning protocol to achieve the vacuum pressure for a desired molecular flow regime. This work validates the breadboard design as an experimental platform for future parabolic flight campaigns and serves as a developmental step towards a lunar payload for *in situ* material handling de-risking.

Highlights

- Designed and manufactured is remotely reconfigurable wedge hopper breadboard for lunar regolith simulants to be tested in lunar like environmental conditions.
- System enables automated static granular material flow characterization in vacuum and 1/6 of Earth gravity conditions.
- Integrated carousel allows multi-sample dosing without compromising vacuum integrity.
- Validated mechanical and electrical reliability of the breadboard in a laboratory vacuum chamber.
- Hardware architecture is optimized for parabolic flight and ISRU mission de-risking.

Keywords

Lunar environment, lunar gravity, wedge hopper breadboard, lunar regolith simulants, vacuum chamber, outgassing, parabolic flight, bulk materials handling

1 Introduction

1.1 Importance of bulk materials-handling for future lunar surface activities

Plans to establish a persistent human presence on the Moon (NASA, 2020; Lin et al. 2024; Wang et al. 2026) rely on the viability of *In-Situ* Resource Utilisation (ISRU) to source and process raw materials for construction and manufacturing (Azami et al. 2024; Badescu et al. 2012; Bennett et al 2020; Crawford 2015; Zhang et al.2023; Wang et al. 2025). A critical, yet often under-represented feature of ISRU is the effective handling of local granular materials (regolith) within the unique lunar environment.

The specific conditions of the lunar surface - characterised by reduced gravity (1/6 g), a hard vacuum exosphere, and the distinctive properties of lunar regolith such as high cohesiveness, abrasiveness, and angular particle morphology - pose substantial engineering challenges (Walton et al. 2007; Walton 2012; Shaw et al 2022). Standard terrestrial excavation, transportation, and feeding techniques cannot be assumed to function reliably in this environment without significant modification and validation (Just et al. 2020; Just et al. 2024; Zacny 2012). Therefore, an understanding of unique regolith material handling phenomena to aid in the development of lunar handling technologies are important for the progression of lunar exploration and operations.

1.2 *The need for in situ validation of material handling knowledge*

While terrestrial bulk material handling is a mature field, this knowledge is not directly transferable to the unique context of the lunar surface. Currently, lunar understanding is based on Earth-based simulations - such as drop towers, parabolic flights, and the use of regolith simulants - and numerical models (e.g., Discrete Element Method) (Belser et al. 2016; Pletser et al. 2010; Pletser 2015; Laemmerzahl et al. 2015; Pratnekar et al. 2025). However, there is a fundamental concern regarding the validity of these results, as they have not been validated or calibrated against material handling processes in actual lunar environmental conditions with real lunar materials.

This lack of *in situ* validation creates a knowledge gap that poses a risk of hardware failure or inefficiency for future lunar activities. Misconceptions regarding lunar granular material behaviour could lead to poor operational performance, including system clogging or incomplete discharge and material transfers. Ultimately, these issues could render ISRU technology unreliable and unsustainable. To address this, the "Materials Utilisation for a Lunar Economy" (MULE) project has been proposed by the authors and colleagues (Pratnekar et al. 2025). The MULE concept outlines a dedicated lunar payload designed to take a "pragmatic approach" to generating *in situ* datasets. Rather than purely scientific measurement, MULE focuses on observing practical material handling subsystems - such as excavation, conveying, and hopper discharge - directly on the lunar surface to de-risk, validate, and calibrate Earth-based simulations and technology.

1.3 *Context of the current work: The Hopper Breadboard*

This paper focuses on the early development of one specific element of the proposed MULE payload architecture: the static handling subsystem, specifically a reconfigurable wedge hopper. The work presented here details the design, manufacture, and initial testing of a remotely reconfigurable wedge hopper breadboard. This breadboard is specifically designed to bridge the gap between laboratory testing and the lunar surface by being able to operate within a vacuum chamber during reduced-gravity parabolic flights. By replicating the lunar environment more accurately than standard ground tests, this breadboard serves two purposes: it generates high-fidelity data to begin the validation of material handling models, and it serves as a critical development framework for the flight-ready hardware intended for the future MULE lunar mission. Specifically, this paper describes the development and initial testing of the breadboard (basic vacuum compatibility with mechanical and electrical control functions) prior to use in parabolic flight at appropriate vacuum pressures corresponding to free molecular flow regimes.

2 **Justification for the reconfigurable wedge hopper breadboard**

2.1 *The role of hoppers in ISRU*

In the context of future lunar ISRU architectures, hoppers will function as critical nodes within the material handling chain. Their primary roles are threefold: filling (receiving bulk granular material from excavation or conveying systems), static storage (holding material to act as a buffer between asynchronous processes), and discharging (dosing material into subsequent subsystems such as reactors, sorters, or secondary conveyors) (Noe 2024). The reliability of these stages is important; a failure in discharge, such as a blockage, effectively halts the downstream production line. In the lunar environment, where maintenance is difficult, the hopper design should allow continuous, controlled, and minimal dust-generation transfer of regolith under lunar gravity and vacuum conditions (Watson et al. 2024).

For this research and development work, a specific geometry known as a wedge hopper was selected. Unlike the more common conical hopper (which narrows from a circular base to a point), a wedge hopper features a rectangular or square top that tapers down to a long, narrow slit-like outlet (Schulze 2008). Specific geometric characteristics - namely the inclination of the side walls and the width of the outlet slit - directly dictate the flow behaviour and potential failure modes of the stored granular material (Lu et al. 2022). A significant benefit of the wedge hopper design for experimental validation is that the frontal and rear walls are flat. When manufactured from transparent material, these flat surfaces allow for clear, undistorted optical recording of the bulk material behaviour inside, making it an appropriate choice for a breadboard and flight-model designed to record visual validation datasets.

2.2 *Theory of bulk solids flow and discharge regimes*

To design reliable hoppers and interpret experimental data, it is necessary to understand the fundamental flow regimes of bulk solids. While theoretical frameworks such as those outlined by Jenike (1964) provide methods for calculating critical outlet dimensions based on material properties (shear strength, internal friction, wall friction), the primary focus of this study is the observation of the resulting flow or discharge behaviours. These behaviours generally fall into two categories of flow and two categories of flow obstruction:

- **Mass Flow:** This is the ideal regime for most applications. Every particle in the hopper moves whenever any material is withdrawn. This "first-in, first-out" pattern ensures a uniform residence time, minimises segregation, and provides a steady discharge rate. It typically requires steeper wall angles and low wall friction.

- **Funnel Flow (Core Flow):** Material flows primarily through a central channel above the outlet, while material at the hopper walls remains stagnant (dead zones). This results in a "first-in, last-out" pattern. While functional, it makes the system prone to ratholing and reduces the effective storage capacity.
- **Arching (Bridging):** A flow obstruction where a stable arch forms across the outlet, supporting the weight of the material above and completely stopping flow. This occurs when the outlet is too narrow relative to the cohesive strength of the material.
- **Ratholing:** A flow obstruction associated with funnel flow, where the central core empties, leaving a stable vertical hole (rathole) surrounded by stagnant material that does not collapse into the outlet.

These regimes are governed by the interplay between the hopper geometry (wall angle, outlet width) and the bulk material properties - and in a lunar context, changed gravity. By varying the geometry, a single test system can induce and observe examples of these different states.

2.3 The influence of the lunar environment on hopper performance

The flow behaviours described are well-documented in terrestrial environments, but the unique context of the Moon introduces variables that significantly alter performance. The most obvious factor is reduced gravity (1/6 g). While a lower gravity reduces the self-weight and compaction stresses within the stored regolith, it simultaneously reduces the gravitational force driving discharge. Consequently, the relative magnitude of inter-particle cohesive forces increases, potentially making arching and ratholing more likely than on Earth for the same geometry (D'Angelo et al. 2025; Gaida et al 2025 Madden et al 2025).

Secondly, the hard vacuum of the lunar exosphere removes the effects of interstitial gas. On Earth, air pressure gradients within the particle matrix can assist flow (aeration) or hinder it (vacuum interlocking) (Zhu et al. 2020). In a lunar vacuum, these fluidisation effects are absent - i.e. operating in a free molecular flow regime (Yuu et al. 2011; Noe 2024). Furthermore, the extreme cleanliness of particle surfaces in a vacuum - i.e. lacking interaction with molecular components common in other environmental settings such as air and water on Earth - can increase inter-particle friction and cohesion (Perko et al. 2001). Finally, the nature of lunar regolith itself - specifically its tendency to accumulate electrostatic charge and its extreme desiccation - further enhances cohesive effects compared to terrestrial materials (Bailey 1984, Heiken et al. 1991; Walton 2007). Therefore, a hopper design that functions reliably on Earth may fail on the Moon, necessitating test systems that can isolate and replicate these specific environmental variables.

2.4 Gap in existing experimental breadboards

A major limitation of currently available wedge hopper test systems is their rigid, non-reconfigurable design. Typically, these setups allow for the testing of a single geometry (fixed wall angle and outlet) with a single bulk material sample per experimental run. To investigate different flow regimes or failure modes, the hardware must be manually disassembled and modified, or multiple different hoppers must be used (Nakashima et al. 2010). Furthermore, with few exceptions (Reiss et al. 2014), existing breadboards are restricted to operation in Earth gravity and atmosphere.

This lack of versatility limits the ability to generate appropriate datasets efficiently, especially in constrained access environments like vacuum chambers or parabolic flights where manual intervention is challenging. Our proposed breadboard addresses this gap by featuring a remotely reconfigurable geometry (adjustable wall angle and outlet width) and a multi-sample dosing system. This allows for the autonomous testing of multiple material samples under varying geometric conditions within a single vacuum cycle or flight campaign, providing a suitable platform for de-risking future lunar payloads.

3 Design and manufacture of the remotely reconfigurable wedge hopper breadboard with automatic sample dosing

3.1 Introduction

This section details the translation of the experimental needs identified in Section 2 into a physical hardware solution capable of generating two distinct and critical levels of validation datasets. The first, an intermediate dataset, will be generated by operating the current breadboard within a vacuum chamber operating at pressures representing free molecular flow regimes during lunar-gravity parabolic flights. This would provide a substantial improvement over current state-of-the-art ground testing by combining vacuum with reduced gravity, while the multi-sample dosing capability significantly increases experimental throughput. The second, ultimate dataset, refers to the future application where an evolution of this breadboard is deployed as a lunar payload to generate "ground truth" knowledge of handling actual lunar materials in the real lunar environment. The primary goal of this section, therefore, was to design and manufacture a breadboard that can demonstrate the material handling processes of filling, static storage, and discharge to support both these validation pathways, while adhering to the "pragmatic approach" outlined in the MULE project philosophy.

To achieve this, the design process prioritised three core functional requirements: multi-sample dosing capability, remote reconfigurability of the hopper geometry, and remote recovery from flow obstruction. The following

subsections outline the formal requirements, the iterative development process involving a manual prototype, and the final design, manufacture, and assembly of the automated system.

3.2 Breadboard requirements

The top-level design requirements were driven by the constraints of the test environments (vacuum chamber and parabolic flight) and the need for data acquisition.

Operational Requirements: The breadboard must be compatible with vacuum environments, ensuring the suppression of atmospheric drag and associated fluidisation effects. This requires materials and components and pre-treatments that minimise outgassing. The system must also withstand the altered-gravity phases of a lunar-gravity parabolic flight.

Functional Requirements:

- **Multi-sample Dosing:** Because the vacuum chamber cannot be opened mid-flight to reload samples due to vacuum pump down times, the system must store and sequentially dispense multiple discrete samples (pragmatically defined as seven samples of 70 mL each) to maximise data return per flight campaign.
- **Remote Reconfigurability:** To investigate different flow regimes (e.g., mass flow vs. funnel flow) without direct human intervention, the hopper's side wall inclination and bottom outlet width must be remotely adjustable between individual test runs whilst in vacuum.
- **Remote Recovery:** In the event of a flow obstruction / blockage (no discharge), the system must be capable of remotely reconfiguring to a "clearing" state to release the material and reset for the next sample.

Physical and Interface Requirements: The system must fit within a vacuum chamber and pumping system that could be transported to, and used in, a parabolic flight campaign (Pletser et al 2010; Pletser et al 2015). This imparts limits to size, mass and electrical power of a suitable vacuum system. Readily available to the authors was an Applied Vacuum Engineering (AVE) VC-12VF glass cylinder (301 mm ID, 356 mm height) vacuum chamber (Applied Vacuum Engineering Ltd. Web Page) pumped by an Agilent TPS-mini combined turbomolecular pump, diaphragm backing pump (Agilent Technologies, Inc. Web Page) and a Pirani and Penning combination pressure gauge and which meets these requirements. Therefore, the breadboard must fit within this example vacuum system. To enable external video recording, the hopper body must be transparent and allow for unobstructed lines of sight. Note that the video recording and lighting equipment are not part of the breadboard itself; they are positioned outside the vacuum chamber to simplify the breadboard hardware design. The breadboard need only provide the optical access required for these external systems. Future breadboard versions

would integrate video recording and lighting representing the eventual requirements for a lunar flight implementation.

3.3 Intermediate development: The manual breadboard

Prior to the development of the fully automated system, a simplified, manually operated wedge hopper was designed and manufactured. This intermediate step served to de-risk the fundamental geometry concepts. The main body consisted of two parallel transparent acrylic plates (180 mm x 180 mm). The side walls were adjustable via screw rods, allowing for the manual setting of wall inclination and outlet width. Samples were hand-filled, and discharge was initiated by sliding manual plates. This manual version successfully validated the use of acrylic for optical observation and confirmed that the proposed geometric ranges could induce the flow regimes of interest, providing a foundation for the subsequent automation of the design (Pratnekar et al 2025).

3.4 Design and manufacture of the remotely reconfigurable breadboard

Building on the manual prototype, the final reconfigurable breadboard was designed to be operated remotely using computer-controlled stepper motors. The system was manufactured using a combination of FDM 3D printing and CO₂ laser cutting for structural components and Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) mechanical and electronic parts to ensure timely and cost-effective delivery.

3.4.1 General Description

The automated breadboard comprises three vertical arranged levels: a top-mounted carousel sample dosing device, the central reconfigurable wedge hopper, and a bottom sample collection container. The entire assembly is sized to fit inside the specified vacuum chamber (Figure 1). To minimise the number of vacuum feedthroughs required, the control electronics and stepper motors are housed directly on the breadboard structure inside the vacuum environment, requiring only power and data connections to pass via the chamber feedthroughs.

3.4.2 Main Hopper Body

The construction of the main hopper body follows a logical assembly sequence starting with the fixed external frame, followed by the internal variable geometry, and finally the discharge mechanism. First, the fixed frame is established by two parallel, vertical transparent acrylic plates, each measuring 150 mm × 150 mm with a thickness of 10 mm. These plates are manufactured using CO₂ laser cutting and are held in a fixed parallel geometry with a 30 mm internal separation by six cylindrical 3D-printed tubular spacers secured by M4 screws. The transparency of these fixed vertical walls is critical, as it allows for the video recording of the internal material discharge behaviour. Second, the two sloping variable geometry walls are positioned between these fixed vertical plates.

These walls (100 mm × 30 mm) are 3D-printed from PETG and define the wedge angle of the hopper. They are designed such that they are attached at both their top and bottom attachment points to linear actuators. This allows their position and inclination to be adjusted remotely via stepper motors, effectively defining four sides of the hopper: two fixed vertical walls and two adjustable sloping walls. Finally, the hopper geometry is completed by the discharge slit at the bottom. This is defined horizontally by the gap between the bottom edges of the two variable sloping walls and the two fixed vertical walls. To control discharge, this gap is normally closed by two rectangular plates (75 mm × 35 mm), also 3D-printed in PETG. These plates act as a shutter mechanism; they are attached to separate stepper motors and are guided within horizontal grooves in the main acrylic body. When closed, they meet to form a flat bottom to the hopper, retaining the sample. To initiate discharge, the motors pull these plates apart rapidly, creating an opening that allows the granular material to flow out.

To minimise vacuum outgassing from 3D printed components, PETG polymer was chosen due to lower water absorption properties compared to other common FDM 3D printing polymers such as PLA. Components were also printed with 100% infill to minimise air-filled voids within the components that could contribute virtual leaks.

This variable / reconfigurable geometry is driven by a total of six NEMA 8-based linear actuator stepper motors (Joy-IT, NEMA 08-04LA) (SIMAC Electronics GmbH Web Page) Three actuators are mounted symmetrically on each lateral side of the hopper body to independently control the top and bottom positions, and hence angles, of the variable geometry walls, and the discharge slide plates. This configuration allows the side walls to be inclined from 55° to 90° from the horizontal (enabling various flow regimes and clearance of blockages) and the bottom discharge slit opening to be varied between 0 to 60 mm (30 mm symmetrically per side). To mitigate sample leakage, sliding friction / jamming, and abrasive wear, brushed seals are integrated into the contact surfaces of all moving parts. Construction parts and motor holders are secured to the main acrylic body using M3 screws threaded into M3 heat-set inserts.

3.4.3 Carousel Dosing Device

Mounted on top of the main hopper geometry is a rotating carousel-type sample dosing device manufactured by FDM 3D printing with PTEG. It is shaped as a 150 mm high cylinder with a 200 mm diameter, divided into eight equal wedge-shaped chambers, each capable of accommodating up to 100 mL volume of bulk granular material. The rotating part of the carousel rotates against a horizontal and fixed bottom plate manufactured from CO₂ laser cut acrylic sheet. In the fixed acrylic bottom plate is cut a wedge-shaped opening that matches the geometry of one of the sections in the rotating part of the carousel.

Thus, as the carousel rotates, each subsequent sample container moves over this opening emptying its contents into the variable walled wedge hopper positioned below and aided by a fixed transfer chute. All sliding contact surfaces between the individual carousel chambers and the platform are sealed with brush seals to prevent sample leakage, reduce sliding friction, jamming and wear and limit cross-contamination. Rotation is driven by a 5 mm connecting axis coupled to a NEMA 17 stepper motor (Joy-IT, NEMA 17-01) (SIMAC Electronics GmbH Web Page).

3.4.4 Bottom sample collection container

To collect multiple discharged samples from the hopper, a rectangular PETG printed sample collection container was designed, printed and positioned below the discharge slit of the hopper. This was sized to contain seven, 70mL samples with a design margin.

3.4.5 Electronics and Control

To minimise the complexity of vacuum feedthroughs, and to allow a standalone breadboard more akin to the vision of a future flight model, the primary control electronics are housed directly on the breadboard within the vacuum chamber. The stepper motors are controlled via a Bigtreetech Octopus V1.1 32-bit control board (Shenzhen BIQU Technology Co., Ltd. Web Page) loaded with Marlin firmware (capable of controlling up to eight stepper motors). The control interface is provided by a Raspberry Pi Model 3+ single-board computer (1.4 GHz 64-bit quad-core ARM Cortex-A53) (Raspberry Pi Holdings plc. Web page). Both the motor controller and the single-board computer are mounted on 3D-printed holders.

External to the vacuum chamber, power is supplied by a Mean Well LRS-150-24 AC/DC power supply (Mean Well Enterprise Co., Ltd. Web page), providing a 24VDC output with a 156W power rating and a maximum current of 6.5A.

Control logic is managed by an open-source Node.js platform JavaScript runtime environment (Node.js Web page) hosted on the single-board computer, functioning as both a web and websocket server. The internal single-board computer communicates with the motor controller via a virtual serial link. Instructions are sent to the single-board computer via a USB link routed through the vacuum feedthrough from a web browser interface running on a PC outside the vacuum chamber. Users interact with this interface to send G-CODE commands to adjust geometry and trigger sample dosing. The system allows specific power states for the motors: ON (moving), HOLD (energised to maintain position during filling), and OFF (de-energised). The OFF state is utilised whenever possible to minimise heat dissipation – an important thermal management strategy in the vacuum environment.

Figure 1. Visualisation of variable wall wedge hopper breadboard with rotating carousel sample dosing system inside the vacuum test chamber (left image - CAD representation of breadboard, right image - photograph of breadboard in vacuum chamber).

4 Breadboard functional testing in representative vacuum conditions with lunar regolith simulants in 1g

4.1 Introduction

This section details the testing and demonstration of the remotely reconfigurable wedge hopper breadboard with automatic sample dosing in a vacuum environment and in a gravity level of 1g. The testing comprises the vacuum chamber system, the video recording system, the hopper breadboard and relevant regolith simulants.

4.2 Vacuum chamber setup

The experimental setup used to provide an appropriate vacuum environment for the breadboard was an Applied Vacuum Engineering (AVE) glass vacuum chamber coupled with an Agilent TPS-mini turbomolecular pump system. The main chamber cylinder is made of glass allowing photo and video recording, with stainless steel top and baseplates. The vacuum pump port in the baseplate of the chamber is additionally protected with a 3D printed baffle-like insert to minimise contamination of the turbomolecular pump system with the granular material. Data logging of the pressure conditions versus time, inside of the vacuum chamber are accomplished with a combination Pirani / Penning vacuum gauge linked to the turbomolecular pump system and read out by custom Python software script running on an external PC, recording data to file at a rate of 1Hz. The tests reported in this section were conducted at pressures that confirmed the mechanical and electrical functionality of the breadboard in a vacuum environment (typically vacuum chamber pressure of 8×10^{-1} mbar), de-risking the system operation

prior to future targeting the stricter molecular flow regimes required for flight.

4.3 Equipment to capture video of the hopper discharge behaviour

Video recording of the experimental runs was conducted using a smartphone camera (Apple iPhone 15) mounted on a fixed tripod, configured to record at 4K resolution with a frame rate of 60 frames per second (fps). Supplemental illumination was provided by two LED video light panels, each measuring 149 mm x 103 mm, with a Correlated Colour Temperature of 5600K and a power output of 10W (Shenzhen Neewer Technology Co., Ltd. Web page). Due to size constraints, both the video and lighting equipment were positioned external to the vacuum chamber, observing the experiment through the chamber's transparent glass walls.

4.4 Lunar regolith material simulants

Primary granular material selected for tests was the European Space Agency (ESA) high-fidelity EAC-1 Lunar regolith simulant (Engelschön et al 2020, Zemeny et al 2024). This simulant was chosen due to its widespread use and validation within the European space community, offering a well-documented and reliable analogue for lunar soil properties. To extend testing of the breadboard functioning and design, tests were additionally performed with a wood flour (Supreme Products Web page), used already in a context of reduced particle density lunar regolith simulants paradigm (Pratnekar et al 2025). Both materials are different in structure, physical properties and flow behaviour, making them appropriate test examples for evaluating the functionality of the breadboard.

4.5 Vacuum chamber and 1g demonstration of the reconfigurable wedge hopper breadboard functionality

A standardised procedure was established for the filling and discharge of test samples to and from the reconfigurable hopper. To characterise the flow and material behaviour of granular media, three distinct hopper settings - shallow, intermediate, and steep - were used. Furthermore, a protocol for blocked or jammed hopper discharge was established to enable complete remote operation of the breadboard in the event of partial or full hopper geometry obstruction.

4.5.1 Standard protocol for filling and releasing of the test sample

The standard experimental protocol begins with the filling sequence. The top-mounted eight-position carousel, loaded with seven individual granular samples (each of 70mL volume) and initially aligned with the cutout in the fixed bottom plate, rotates clockwise at approximately 8 deg/s. This action realigns a filled carousel chamber with the cutout in the bottom plate and the transfer chute, releasing a single sample into the preconfigured wedge hopper. The material is then allowed to settle within the

hopper body. To initiate hopper discharge, the bottom shutter plates (initially in a closed position blocking the discharge slit) are symmetrically translated horizontally apart via the corresponding stepper motors at a controlled rate (typically 20 mm/s) opening the discharge slit. This allows the sample to release freely under gravity into the collection container below. The resulting discharge characteristics are governed by the specific hopper geometry settings (wall inclination and discharge slit dimension), the material properties, and the gravitational environment. Throughout this process, the flow behaviour is recorded by the video system for subsequent analysis. A sequence of video frames taken from a representative video are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** illustrating this protocol. If the sample discharges completely, the shutter plates are symmetrically closed to close the discharge slit. However, if the material fails to fully exit the hopper (e.g., due to arching or ratholing), a recovery or "cleaning" procedure is initiated. To clear the blockage, the hopper walls are driven to a vertical inclination (90 deg) and the outlet is expanded to its maximum width of 60 mm. Once the hopper is verified to be empty, the cycle repeats with the geometry reconfigured for the next test and the carousel then rotates to dispense the next sample.

Figure 2: (a) $t=0.0s$, carousel starts to rotate; (b) $t=1.0s$, sample starts to fill the hopper; (c) $t=3.0s$, sample is filling the hopper; (d) $t=5.0s$, sample is filling the hopper; (e) $t=6.0s$, filling procedure is completed; (f) $t=11.0s$, sample settles down inside the hopper; (g) $t=12.0s$, slit doors open, sample starts to release; (h) $t=13.0s$ sample is releasing the hopper; (i) $t=14.0s$ sample is releasing the hopper; (j) $t=15.0s$ sample is completely discharged from the hopper

collection container.

4.5.2 Reconfigurable hopper standard settings

Whilst a wide combination of hopper wall angle and discharge slit width could be set, for initial testing three combinations of hopper wall inclination angles (measured from the horizontal in degrees) and hopper bottom opening (in millimetres) were defined as follows (and shown in Figure 3).

- shallow setting (57.5 ± 2.5 deg, 10mm) (Figure 2a)

- intermediate setting (72.5 ± 2.5 deg, 25mm) (Figure 2b)
- steep setting (77.5 ± 2.5 deg, 40mm) (Figure 2c)

This range of combinations, for regolith simulants with appropriate properties, was able to demonstrate the various types of hopper discharge envisaged.

Figure 2. Photographs of the three reconfigurable hopper standard settings named: (a) shallow, (b) intermediate, (c) steep. Also shown is a photograph of the hopper extreme setting to enable recovery from blocked/jammed material discharge and comprising vertical side walls with maximum discharge slit width (d) and (e).

4.5.3 Examples of different flow or discharge behaviours

Testing different granular materials inside the reconfigurable hopper breadboard, four flow or discharge behaviours are expected to occur: full discharge with mass flow, full discharge with funnel or core flow, partial discharge (ratholing effect) and no discharge (bridging or arching). Full discharge is defined as a flow pattern where the entire volume of granular material within the hopper is in motion during discharge, leading to complete emptying of the vessel. This phenomenon is classified under two primary flow regimes. Mass Flow commonly occurs when the hopper walls are sufficiently steep and smooth to minimise wall friction, ensuring that all material is simultaneously in motion. In this regime, the material moves in a first-in, first-out (FIFO) sequence, promoting uniform residence time. The second is Funnel Flow (Core Flow), which occurs when the material at the centre moves preferentially in a first-in, last-out (FILO) sequence. Despite this central movement, funnel flow can still achieve full discharge without leading to severe or permanent stagnant zones, provided the entire vessel

eventually empties. Partial discharge describes a flow pattern characterised by the formation of a stable, vertical flow channel directly above the outlet. The granular material outside this channel remains completely stagnant. This stagnation is caused by the cohesive strength of the bulk material, which allows it to adhere to itself and the hopper walls. This cohesive strength is sufficiently high to resist the shear forces required to initiate and sustain material sliding along the hopper surfaces. No discharge occurs when the granular material forms a stable, self-supporting arch (or bridge) spanning the entire width of the discharge slot. This arch transfers the vertical load of the material overhead directly to the hopper walls, which consequently reduces the stress exerted on the material immediately above the outlet to a level below its failure strength. In the context of the materials tested, this arching phenomenon is primarily attributed to the cohesive strength inherent in fine powders. Examples of different discharge behaviours are shown Figure 3 and with a variety of hopper wall angles and hopper bottom discharge slit widths.

Figure 3: Showing frames from a series of videos of samples and hopper settings that demonstrate the various hopper discharge features previously mentioned – (a) and (b) mass flow, (c) and (d) core flow, (e) ratholing and (f) arching.

4.5.4 Recovery from blocked/jammed discharge

To allow remote operation, given the lack of direct access during vacuum chamber use during parabolic flight tests, a procedure for releasing regolith simulant in a blocked or jammed reconfigurable hopper breadboard is required. In the case of a partial or complete blockage of the hopper geometry, the design allows the hopper outlet opening to be spread to the maximum dimension (60mm) and walls inclined to vertical if required to release any trapped regolith simulant material. Extreme positions of the hopper walls are presented in Figure 2 d and e. The complete recovery procedure for a blocked or jammed hopper with spreading of the outlet openings to facilitate the release of the test granular material is illustrated in Figure 4.

5 Route forward to lunar gravity parabolic flight with lunar relevant vacuum conditions

5.1 Introduction and benefit of lunar parabolic flight tests

Simulating the lunar environment for regolith handling requires not only suitable vacuum conditions but also a gravity level equivalent to the Moon's. Among the available Earth-based methods for creating reduced gravity (Belser et al. 2016; Laemmerzahl et al. 2015), lunar gravity parabolic flights (Pletser et al. 2010; Pletser 2015) were chosen for this work. These flights are

particularly suitable because they offer sustained periods of lunar gravity - approximately 25 to 35 seconds per parabola, with roughly 30 parabolas per flight. This duration is sufficient to demonstrate each key step in the hopper's operation: filling, emptying, and recovering from blockages. The combination of sustained reduced gravity and the breadboards remotely controlled multi-sample dosing system allows for appropriate experimental throughput. In a single flight, it is possible to test up to seven different regolith simulants combined with various hopper settings. Additionally, parabolic flights typically offer the payload capacity (in terms of mass, volume, and operator access) needed to fly the small vacuum chamber system and the hopper breadboard described in this paper.

In Europe, flight campaigns are provided by the European Space Agency (ESA) in collaboration with Novaspace using an A310 ZERO-G aircraft that has been specially modified to replicate zero-gravity, Martian, or lunar gravity conditions. A standard campaign usually comprises three flights, conducted on consecutive days (Novaspace Web page).

Figure 4 Images are video frames from a video sequence of the hopper breadboard operation under vacuum showing examples of steps in the recovery procedure from a blocked hopper and comprising: (a) blocked hopper with bottom slit open; (b), (c), (d) adjusting wall angles and hopper bottom outlet, seeing material falling out; (e) wall angles and hopper bottom outlet adjusted to maximum and seeing no material present .

5.2 Outgassing challenges

Achieving relevant lunar vacuum conditions for regolith handling simulations within the vacuum chamber requires establishing pressures that correspond to a molecular flow regime at length scales pertinent to interparticle distances (approximately 2×10^{-4} mbar). However, challenges arise due to potential outgassing from both the breadboard hardware and the regolith simulant samples. To mitigate this, common practice involves selecting appropriate materials and employing pre-treatment strategies in vacuum ovens to reduce outgassing levels, ensuring the desired vacuum chamber pressure can be achieved within a reasonable pump-down time. For the current study, a Gallenkamp OVL-570-010J laboratory vacuum oven (Gallenkamp Web page), equipped with a BACOENG BA-1 single-stage rotary vane oil-sealed vacuum pump (BACOENG Web page), was used. The oven temperature and duration of treatment were varied as needed to optimise the outgassing reduction process.

5.2.1 Managing outgassing from breadboard

During the breadboard design phase, including component selection and construction, no vacuum-rated materials or electronic components, such as stepper motors, were specified due to financial constraints. All 3D FDM printed components were manufactured using PETG with 100% material infill to minimise outgassing and the potential for trapped internal voids. Consequently, a certain level of outgassing was anticipated.

Figure 5 illustrates the vacuum chamber pump-down rates for the hopper breadboard in three distinct states: prior to any vacuum oven pre-treatment, following initial pre-treatment, and after subsequent cycles of vacuum chamber pump-down combined with brief exposure (tens of minutes) to the ambient laboratory atmosphere. This latter condition represents typical usage during repeated hopper testing. The vacuum oven pre-treatment, or prebaking, involved exposing the breadboard to a temperature of 60°C (chosen to avoid damage of electrical components) under vacuum for 5 hours. The pump-down profile for the untreated breadboard demonstrated significant outgassing, with the vacuum chamber pressure remaining nearly four orders of magnitude higher (1.7 mbar) than the desired upper limit after more than 12 hours of pumping. Following the initial prebaking, the pump-down profile improved substantially: a pressure of approximately 5×10^{-1} mbar was reached within 15 minutes, followed by a further significant decrease to approximately 1×10^{-3} mbar within one hour. Subsequently, the pressure reduced more slowly, falling below the required limit after a total of approximately 6 hours. Subsequent cycles of vacuum chamber pump-down exhibited slightly faster pump-down times - typically in about 3 hours - confirming compatibility with typical operational use.

Figure 5. Demonstration of hopper breadboard outgassing and vacuum oven pre-treatment to minimise outgassing to acceptable levels. The three pump-down profiles shown correspond to the hopper breadboard inside the vacuum chamber, with the chamber pressure logged as a function of pump-down time. The three profiles illustrate: the problematic outgassing observed without pre-treatment (green profile); the immediate improvement following vacuum oven pre-treatment of the breadboard (blue profile), which attains the desired operational pressure (indicated by the horizontal red line); and an example of a subsequent repeat cycle of vacuum chamber pump-down. This final profile (purple profile) follows opening the chamber to atmospheric pressure for a few tens of minutes - e.g., to clean and refill the sample carousel - and demonstrates the ability to attain operational pressure within a useable timescale.

5.2.2 Managing outgassing from material simulants

Regolith simulants are known to exhibit significant outgassing due to their high surface area. To confirm that appropriate vacuum oven pre-treatment could reduce outgassing to acceptable levels - specifically, enabling a vacuum chamber pressure of 2×10^{-4} mbar to be attained with a few hours of pump-down - representative regolith simulants were tested in a vacuum chamber both before and after exposure to a temperature of 120°C in a vacuum oven for 3 hours. 70 mL samples were spread on stainless steel trays, pre-baked in the vacuum oven, cooled, and then transferred to the vacuum chamber for pump-down. Similar samples without pre-baking were also tested for comparison. Tests conducted with EAC-1 and wood flour (a reduced particle density regolith simulant (Pratnekar et al 2025)) confirmed that significant outgassing occurred without pre-baking. However, following pre-baking, the desired vacuum chamber pressure could be reached within an operationally acceptable time of approximately 2 hours for EAC-1 and 4 hours for wood flour. (data not shown).

5.3 Logistic and engineering of vacuum chamber on lunar parabolic flights

The existing breadboard and vacuum chamber hardware were designed and chosen to be compatible with the flight safety and interface requirements dictated by a typical parabolic flight aircraft operator (Novaspace Web page). The primary adaptation required for flight will be the integration of the vacuum chamber into an aluminium space frame. This frame serves multiple functions: it provides a rigid mounting point for securing the experiment to the aircraft's floor mounting rails; it acts as a chassis for mounting peripheral components such as the external control laptop PC, power distribution unit, and video camera lighting; and it supports a transparent polycarbonate shield surrounding the glass vacuum chamber. This shield is required to contain any debris in the unlikely event of a vacuum chamber implosion. Additionally, the frame will be padded with high-density foam to protect operators from impact injuries during the

reduced or hypergravity phases of flight. A representative image of such a setup is given in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Indicative CAD representation of the parabolic flight version showing experimental rack consisting of aluminium space frame, vacuum system including glass vacuum chamber and pump system, LED video lighting panels, video recording devices and controlling PC unit – not shown, high-density foam padding, transparent polycarbonate implosion shield windows in space frame. Also indicated, the aircraft cabin floor with mounting rails.

5.4 Outline experimental protocol for parabolic flight

The current breadboard configuration, featuring a carousel capable of housing seven samples, is well-suited for a standard three-day three-flight parabolic flight campaign. With approximately 30 parabolas available per flight, a single experimental run for one sample typically spans multiple parabolas to capture the full sequence of filling, settling, discharge, and potential blockage recovery. Therefore, the capacity to test seven discrete samples per flight allows four parabolas per sample, allowing for a total of approximately 21 distinct experimental runs over the course of a three-flight campaign.

The intended operational protocol is designed to eliminate the need for opening the vacuum chamber during flight, as the pump-down time from atmospheric pressure to operational pressure would far exceed the available flight duration. Instead, the chamber will be loaded with samples and pumped down on the ground prior to takeoff. Once the target vacuum chamber pressure is achieved, the chamber is sealed, and the vacuum pump powered down for takeoff in accordance with typical safety regulations. After takeoff and prior to the first parabola, the pump is restarted to maintain the vacuum level against any outgassing, ensuring the experiment operates in the required pressure regime during experimental runs.

6 Discussion and conclusions

This study details the design, manufacture, and initial testing of a remotely reconfigurable, multi-sample wedge hopper breadboard tailored for operation in a vacuum chamber during reduced-gravity parabolic flights. The system successfully demonstrates the capability to perform remote filling, static storage, and controlled discharge of granular materials - key processes identified in the MULE project architecture. The inclusion of a seven-sample dosing carousel and a remotely adjustable hopper geometry allows for high-throughput testing of diverse flow regimes (e.g., mass flow vs. funnel flow) and recovery from failure modes (e.g., arching) without direct human intervention, a critical requirement for constrained parabolic and eventually lunar flight environments.

While functional testing confirmed the mechanical robustness of the breadboard using commercial-off-the-shelf components and 3D-printed parts, vacuum characterisation highlighted the significant challenge of outgassing. Initial tests showed that standard materials prevented the system from reaching the target molecular flow regime (2×10^{-4} mbar) within a flight-relevant timeline. However, the implementation of a vacuum bake-out protocol (60°C for the hardware, 120°C for simulants) demonstrated a viable path forward, significantly reducing pump-down times to operationally acceptable levels. This

finding underscores the necessity of rigorous thermal vacuum conditioning for all flight hardware and samples prior to integration on the aircraft.

This breadboard serves as a vital intermediate validation step, bridging the gap between terrestrial lab tests and future lunar surface payloads. By enabling the collection of high-fidelity material handling data under combined vacuum and lunar-gravity conditions, it will provide the "ground truth" needed to validate numerical models and de-risk the design of future ISRU infrastructure. Furthermore, the versatile nature of the platform allows it to serve as a standalone testbed for characterising novel simulants, such as reduced-density wood flour, in reduced pressure environments on Earth.

Acknowledgements

We thank Cranfield University for providing the facilities to perform the studies reported.

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